

NOTES

Studies on Solutions of High Dielectric Constant: Part XII'. Surface Tension of the Solutions of Some Tetra-alkylammonium Iodides in Formamide, N-methylformamide and N-methylacetamide

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In view of the present wide interest in the study of the behaviour³ of the tetraalkylammonium salts and almost complete absence of studies on the surface tension⁴ of their solutions, it has been considered desirable to undertake a systematic investigation of these ions from this point of view. The present note reports some preliminary findings on the surface tension of the solutions of some R₄N-iodides in water, formamide, N-methylformamide, and N-methylacetamide.

EXPERIMENTAL

The salts namely, Me₄NI, Et₄NI, Bu₄NI and KI were suitably purified by repeated crystallisation from appropriate solvents. KI has been included in the investigation in order to have a comparative idea of the behaviours of R₄NI and classical salts and having the same anion. The solvents namely, formamide, N-methylformamide (NMF) and N-methylacetamide (NMA), were purified by repeated vacuum distillation, after treatment with freshly ignited quicklime, till their electrical conductance was reduced to about 10⁻⁵ to 10⁻⁶ mhos. The surface tension was measured with a Traube's stalagmometer which was enclosed in an outer glass jacket through which dry nitrogen could be passed, if and when desired. The stalagmometer could be moved up or down at will and was kept in position by a rubber stopper which closed the mouth of the outer jacket. The jacket containing the solution and the stalagmometer, was kept in a thermostat, the temperature of which could be controlled within $\pm 0.03^\circ$. The accuracy of the equipment and of the procedure was ascertained by determining the surface tension of two liquids (alcohol and benzene) and the maximum deviation found being less than $\pm 0.2\%$ which was considered satisfactory for the present work.

Experiments were carried out in an atmosphere of dry nitrogen at 30°, 35° and 40°. The surface tension was calculated in the usual manner from the number of drops and the density of the solution in question. Results obtained are discussed as follows:

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Aqueous solutions: The results obtained indicate that the relative surface tension, $\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0}$, first decreases, passes through a minimum (or appears to do so in cases like Bu_4NI) and finally increases with increase in concentration, with a qualitative similarity to the expected theoretical behaviour^{5,6}. A similar behaviour is reported for the aqueous solutions of KCl and CaNO_3 ^{7,8} (and so one should expect the same behaviour in KI solutions and hence these were not actually examined by us); the minimum reported in these solutions occurs at very low concentrations (in the range 0.0001M to 0.001M) and is, therefore, more or less, of academic interest only. This result (in solutions of common electrolytes like KCl , CaNO_3 , etc.) has been doubted by some workers and is believed to be due to traces of impurities¹⁰ by others. However, for R_4NI solutions, the minimum appears to be beyond doubt and occurs around 0.004M to 0.005M. Repeated experiments gave the same result. These results indicate that the larger the cation, the sharper the decrease in $\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0}$ with rise in concentration. The salts appear to be preferentially adsorbed on the surface phase at the lower concentrations and the salts behave as surface active agents⁴, the surface activity increasing with the increase in the length of R-chains, attached to the R_4N^+ ion.

Solutions in formamide, N-methylformamide and N-methylacetamide:—In contrast with the behaviour in aqueous solutions, the relative surface tension, $\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0}$, now increases (more rapidly than the theoretical¹⁰) with the increase in concentration in the beginning, attains a maximum in 0.05M range in some cases, and then decreases. Thus the solutes, in the beginning at least, are negatively adsorbed on the surface phase and so the salts appear to be lyophilic in these solvents which is opposite to their (except KI and similar salts) behaviour in water.

In view of the preliminary nature of investigations, further comments may be a little premature. It may be remarked, however, that the alkyl chains present in R_4N^+ ions make them hydrophobic in water and thus these salts are preferentially adsorbed on the surface, leading to the lowering of the surface tension. Opposite is the case with the amide and N-alkylsubstituted amide solvents like formamide, NMF and NMA in which the alkyl chains should feel homely and the R_4NI salts have lyophilic nature, leading to preferentially accumulation of the solute in the bulk of the solvents and to the increase in the surface tension with the increase in concentration, at least in the lower concentration range.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY,
LUCKNOW.

Received, April 27, 1967.

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